

WORKERS GOVERNING TECHNOLOGIES

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Workers Governing Technologies? Barcelona Lessons

→ *a zine to spark
dialogue on
platform
cooperativism,
public policy &
democratic
digital futures.*

Why this zine?

- this zine is a collective tool for reflection. It comes from ongoing research on how Barcelona has experimented with digital commons, cooperatives, and public policy to challenge platform capitalism.
- it departs from the article *Digitalizing the Social and Solidarity Economy in the era of Digital Capitalism*:

"The digitalization of the SSE in Barcelona is not just technical innovation – it is a political experiment in democracy." (Espelt & Vega, 2025)

Mini shared (hopefully) starting glossary

- **Platform Capitalism** → corporate digital platforms extracting value through data + precarious labour.
- **Digital Commons** → shared infrastructures for collective use and care.
- **Social and Solidarity Economy (SSE)** → cooperatives, associations, and networks driven by justice, equity, and sustainability rather than profit.
- **Policy Co-creation** → participatory processes where citizens, researchers, institutions, and communities design policies together.
- **Action Research** → research done *with* people, not *on* people – combining investigation, participation, and transformation.
- **Platform Cooperativism** → worker-owned and democratically governed digital platforms.

Barcelona as a social and technopolitical laboratory

The city has become a pioneer in digital commons policies (like Decidim and open data initiatives), incubators (such as La Comunicadora), and support programs for platform cooperatives (MatchImpulsa).

These efforts are rooted in a **strong community ecosystem**:

- **Networks and entities** such as the Solidarity Economy Network of Catalonia (XES), the Federation of Worker Cooperatives of Catalonia and the Third Sector Platform of Catalonia.
- **Spaces of experimentation** like Canòdrom (digital and democratic innovation) and Bloc4BCN (community-driven cooperative hub).

Mini-timeline: Socio-economic & technopolitical innovation (Barcelona, 2016–2023)

- * 2016-2017 → Procomuns (policy co-creation)
 - 4 open sessions → 120 policy proposals, 87 incorporated into Barcelona's 2017 Municipal Action Plan (PAM). 300+ participants across a quadruple-helix process (administration, movements, tech, academia).
- ** 2018-2019 → Sharing Cities (from local to translocal)
 - Process engaging ~50 cities, culminating in the Sharing Cities Declaration (2018) signed by 33 cities with 14 policy axes for platform governance, digital sovereignty, and commons-oriented infrastructures.
- *** 2016-2021 → La Comunificadora (commons-oriented incubation)
 - 5 editions, 60+ initiatives accompanied from concept to prototyping (e.g., Som Mobilitat, Katuma, CommonsCloud, FreeSound). Widely recognized as a bridging incubator between technical practice and political horizons.
- **** 2020-2023 → MatchImpulsa (feminist platformization of the SSE)
 - Program with 300+ entities engaged overall; 125+ organizations trained; 27 accelerated; 8 co-financed via matchfunding. Built shared resources (digitESSt, digiTeca, Digital Data Lab) and linked with BcnFemTech; parity criteria set at ≥ 40% women/non-binary.

Axis 1 → Policy co-creation: * Procomuns, ** Sharing Cities.

Axis 2 → Socio-economic innovation (commons-oriented):
*** La Comunificadora, **** MatchImpulsa.

Opportunities & Potentials

Barcelona's ecosystem shows how policy, grassroots movements, and academia can align to push back against platform capitalism and build democratic digital futures.

Gains so far

- **Cooperatives challenging platform monopolies**
 - 4 open sessions → 120 policy proposals, 87 incorporated initiatives like Som Mobilitat, Katuma, and CommonsCloud are proving that digital infrastructures can be governed collectively.
- **Feminist tech policies**
 - the BcnFemTech government measure and programs like MatchImpulsa set gender equity standards ($\geq 40\%$ women/non-binary) in training and governance.
- **Commons infrastructures**
 - platforms like Decidim and open data policies demonstrate how digital democracy can be scaled and institutionalized.
- **International impact**
 - Barcelona's Sharing Cities Declaration was signed by 33 cities, making digital sovereignty a translocal agenda.
- **Intercooperation**
 - programs like La Comunicadora have incubated more than 60 initiatives, creating bridges between tech communities, activists, and public administration.
- **Academia as a driver of analysis & resources**
 - research groups not only provide frameworks and methodologies to assess digitalization, but also bring in research-action projects and funding, reinforcing the ecosystem with knowledge and long-term perspectives.
- **Practical resources**
 - beyond training and incubation, the program has created tools for the ecosystem: 1) digitESSt: for self-diagnosis; 2) digiTeca: for training and capacity-building; 3) Digital Data Lab: as a data repository to support evidence-based strategies.

Challenges & Tensions

The digitalization of the Social and Solidarity Economy (SSE) in Barcelona has shown great promise – but also faces serious structural obstacles:

→ Scarce resources & limited digital skills

→ Many cooperatives and third-sector entities dedicate less than 2% of their budget to digitalization. Training and accessible tools are often missing.

→ Dependency on commercial infrastructures

→ Despite building alternatives, most SSE initiatives still rely on corporate platforms and proprietary tools, which limits sovereignty and autonomy.

→ Gender gaps & unequal access

→ Despite initiatives such as BcnFemTech, women and non-binary people remain underrepresented in leadership and technology roles. Even within feminized sectors like the SSE, a persistent gap exists between stated values and the actual implementation of feminist practices.

→ City council governance

→ Municipal support (Procomuns, Decidim, MatchImpulsa) has been essential to seed projects. Yet these policies depend on political cycles, budget priorities, and shifting agendas. Without stable long-term commitment, gains risk being reversed or fragmented.

→ Difficulties scaling beyond the local

→ Barcelona has provided fertile ground for experimentation, yet without strong institutional backing and financial support, replication in other regions remains difficult and local innovations risk isolation. At the European level, the promoted "twin transition" (digital and green) does not always translate into effective support for social and solidarity economy initiatives, leaving a gap between policy discourse and concrete backing..

→ Tension line linked to electoral cycles

→ Resistance exists – but without stable alliances and community-supported initiatives, it risks being fragmented, underfunded, or co-opted.

Your turn

→ Notes, doodles, demands, ideas... this space is yours.

Credits

- most of the research and reflections presented in this zine come from the work of the Dimmons research group team at the Universitat Oberta de Catalunya with the support of Barcelona City Council and Barcelona Activa, the local development agency.
- the impact of the MatchImpulsa program has been extensively studied in Nuria Vega's doctoral thesis, supervised by Ricard Espelt.
- this zine also connects to Enric Senabre's Ramon & Cajal research project Common Margin and the pliegOS project team, hosted by the cooperative femProcomuns.

Presenter

- Ricard Espelt is Professor and researcher in Social and Solidarity Economy and digitalization at the Universitat Oberta de Catalunya. Social and cultural activist, co-founder of femProcomuns, (des)vestint aliments, and the inLoft Cultural Center.

Want to know more or share a proposal?

- Write to me: ricardespelt@uoc.edu

← Scan to down this zine

